

COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE

Jumaniyazova Nargiza Abdugafurovna,

Teacher of the "Department of Exact and Natural Sciences,
Fergana State University Correspondence Department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7583963>

Abstract: For centuries, each nation has been interested in and studied the history, customs and literature of another nation, while the literature of each nation was formed along with its history and traditions. Proceeding from this, simultaneously with the emergence of contacts between peoples, generally similar traditions and trends, trends in literature arose. Especially after independence, literary ties between English, Russian and Uzbek literature intensified, many translated works were created. This is stated in the article.

Keywords: plot, composition, everyday problems, comparative typological analysis.

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНО-ТИПОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ УЗБЕКСКОЙ И АНГЛИЙСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ.

Аннотация: На протяжении веков каждый народ интересовался и изучал историю, обычаи и литературу другого народа, в то время как литература каждого народа формировалась вместе с его историей и традициями. Исходя из этого, одновременно с возникновением контактов между народами возникли в целом схожие традиции и веяния, направления в литературе. Особенно после обретения независимости усилились литературные связи между английской, русской и узбекской литературой, было создано много переведенных произведений. Об этом говорится в статье.

Ключевые слова: сюжет, композиция, бытовые проблемы, сравнительно-типологический анализ.

INTRODUCTION

The field of comparative typological analysis includes various aspects-themes, ideas, trends, emotions, plot, composition, style. Although comparative typological analysis actually explores more similarities, but there are many literary phenomena separated by a lot of time and space, difficult to understand, incomparable with any social and historical conditions, which at the same time surprise us with their extreme degree of similarity.

The most interesting thing in the science of literary criticism is that the literature of no nation, no country can be singled out and studied separately. Because literature is such a complex process, such a unified system, which is formed from its development thanks to the interaction of literatures of different nationalities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

“Compared to language, which is an everyday means of communication, the language of fiction is a language processed by the masters of the word.”

Thus, language, translation is a weapon of spiritual communication between peoples. For many years, literature of different nationalities has been exchanging translation tools among themselves, enriching each other. People of different nationalities, studying literature in other languages, bring the same literary trends and trends into their language, receiving spiritual pleasure and inspiration from them. Therefore, works that are close and similar to each other in composition, plot, flow and direction appear in world literature.

Such artifacts do not arise by themselves. Literary translation plays a huge role in this. Not every directly created work is easily perceived in literature. The translator must instill in the

translated work such a spirit that it can be adapted to the spirit of the translated nation, while not compromising the original literature. The translator must have a large and free vocabulary in both languages, be able to use artistic means on the spot.

RESULTS

People who have brought samples of world literature to Uzbek literature through translation are actually writers or poets themselves. Among them are such as Chulpan, Abdullah Kadiri, Maksud Sheikhzada, Hamid Olimjan. Works translated by people who are not the owners of this field, in most cases, were not successful.

Works reflecting universal goals are the property not only of their own people, but also contribute to the spiritual wealth of people of other nationalities. Representatives of all nationalities are inextricably linked, draw inspiration from each other, enrich each other, develop each other, in whatever field they are, especially in the field of literature and culture. Especially in the field of literature and art, which bring each other new directions, trends, genres, new words, new views appear.

The literature that most attracts our attention at the moment is Russian and American literature. Russian literature studies should be taken into account that it can be recognized that many representatives of Uzbek literary studies with interest the works of representatives of Russian and American literature, representatives of Russian literary studies the works of representatives of Uzbek and American literature, and representatives of American literary studies the works of representatives of Russian and Uzbek literature.

DISCUSSION

An example of how foreigners show great interest in Uzbek literature and culture is the book of the Latin American figure Rudolfo Jold "Uzbekistan in the Mirror", published in 1956 by the Editorial fundamentos publishing house in the capital of Argentina, Ayres.

The work consists of two chapters devoted to the history and geography of Uzbekistan, the contribution to the world literature of such great thinkers of Central Asia as Avicenna, Mirza Ulugbek, Al-Khorezmi, etc. Along with Navoi, Mahmud Kashgari, Furkat, Mukimi, N. Olimjon, It tells about the life and work of such representatives of literature as Yashin too.

Currently, the interest in Uzbek literature abroad can be seen again in the fact that many manuals on the study of the Uzbek language, literature, and history have been created. For example, we can list such books as "Uzbek grammar" Andrey Shoberg, "Anthology of the Uzbek language" Nicholas Popper, "The initial course of the Uzbek language" by Alo Round. An active propagandist of Uzbek literature, the dean of the Faculty of Near Eastern Languages and Cultures at the University of Washington, Professor Ilza Laude Sirtautas, published the book "Anthology of modern Uzbek literature" in 1980.

After gaining independence, the influence of the Uzbek language, literature, and culture increased. There is a growing interest in the work of Uzbek poets and writers from the countries of America, England, Germany, France.

In fact, the development of American-Uzbek literary ties began in the 30s of the last century. The works of American writers in prose and literacy have been translated into Uzbek and published in newspapers and magazines. One of the figures who made the greatest contribution to these literary and cultural ties at that time was Ghafur Ghulam.

Another reason for the development of Uzbek literature in other countries is the invaluable merit of communication, like-minded writers and translators, as well as creative trips between America and Uzbekistan.

At the moment, one of the latest translations is the work of Nurali Kabul "The Great Emir of Turan or Mind and Sword". From the translation of this historical work into English, it is clear that representatives of other nationalities pay great attention to the study of not only literature, but also the history of Uzbekistan. Hashimov's works have long been translated in different years and are read with love by people of other nationalities. Because his works, such as "Horizon", "Affairs of the world", "Notes in a notebook", have been translated into many other languages. And he himself translated K. Simonov, A. Kiplin many works of such writers as Hemingway into Uzbek.

Many of Hashimov's works have been translated not only into English, but also into many other languages and are still read with love by people of other nationalities.

And Faulkner's book consisting of the works "Bear", "Roses for Emily", "September with the flood", "Black Music", you can read in Uzbek. A lot of his works have been translated into Russian in other years.

"Between two Doors" by Hashimov and "Sound and Fury" by Faulkner are works written by people of different nationalities in different space and time.

At the moment, interest in Faulkner's work is also growing.

"Between two doors" by Hashimov and despite the fact that Faulkner's works "Sound and Fury" were written at different times, in different spaces, in different genres, in some aspects they are united.

One of these two works was written in 1929, and the other in 1986 by representatives of literature of different nationalities in different countries. One depicts the First World War, the other shows the life of peoples before and after the Great Patriotic War.

CONCLUSION

Both works are written in a polyphonic style. In modern works, the need for a conceptual approach to such issues as genre, plot, composition, image, style, motive, language of a work of art as a subject of poetics comes to the main agenda. In the novels of Hashimov, William Faulkner, family and family relations are considered as values, there are differences in an individual approach to everyday problems.

Both works reflect psychological processes, people's relationships with each other through feelings, family relationships, and everyday relationships.

The compositional structure and plot of these two works, written in a polyphonic style, are similar.

REFERENCES:

1. A.V. Fedorov. The language and style of the artwork. M, GIHL, 1963
2. "Poetic or spiritual scenes in prose. U.Hoshimov among his contemporaries" Tashkent, 2011.
3. Hoshimov U. "Between two doors" – Tashkent, 2019.
4. Boltaboyev H. "Honorable writer" – Tashkent, 2011.
5. Yulchiyev, K. V. (2019). The category of space and time of tercets. *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*, 2(4), 131-134.
6. Жуманиязова, Н. А. (2022). Тилга Эътибор–Элга Эътибор. *THEORY OF RECENT SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*, 1(2), 130-133.
7. Jumaniyazova, N. A. O. (2022). MALAYSIAN IMPRESSIONS (BASED ON A 2002-2003 SERVICE TRIP). *Scientific progress*, 3(2), 868-873.